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Water Supply Project in Xorgoble, Qardho, Bari Region

Submitted to

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Submitted In Partial Fulfilment of The Requirements for the Award of Degree in

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DECLARATION AND APPROVAL

Declaration of students

We are declaring that this thesis “*Water Supply Project in Xorgoble, Qardho, Bari Region*” is our own work, and cannot be submitted for an award of degree, diploma, or certificate by means from any other university or institution.

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ABSTRACT

The "Water Supply Project in Xorgoble, Qardho, Bari Region" thesis focuses on the future implementation and impact of a water supply project aimed at addressing water scarcity and improving the quality of life in the Xorgoble community. The project's objective is to construct a reliable and sustainable water supply system that would provide clean and accessible water to the residents.

The thesis begins by outlining the context of water scarcity in the country and the challenges faced by the community in accessing safe water. It then describes the planning and implementation process of the water supply project. Over all that points, the thesis discusses the sustainability of the water supply system, emphasizing the importance of community involvement and capacity building.

It's also highlighting the positives that would outcome of this water supply project in Xorgoble, including improvements in health, sanitation, education, and economic opportunities for the community. On the other hand, the project's impact on various demographic groups, with a particular focus on women and children who previously faced significant challenges in accessing safe water. Additionally, the study will explore the project's contribution to employment generation and local economic development.

Lastly, this thesis offers valuable insights into the system of water supply generally in Qardho, and specifically in Xorgoble, providing a comprehensive analysis, and recommendations that will contribute to the existing knowledge of water supply projects in Ministry of water resources (PMoEMW).

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

PMoEMW	Puntland Ministry of Energy Minerals and Water
U. V	Ultra Violet (Radiation)
ADD	Average Daily Demand
MDD	Maximum Daily Demand
M^3/d	Meter Cubic Per Day
PHD	Peak Hour Demand
M^2/s	Meter Cubic Per Second
PH	Power of Hydrogen
$EC(\mu S/cm)$	Electric Conductivity Measured in Micro-Siemens Per Centimeter
$T^{\circ}C$	Temperature Measured in degree Celsius
Mg/l	Milligram Per Liter
PVC	Polyvinyl Chloride (Pipe)
KW	Kilo Watt
M^2/h	Meter Squared Per Hour
DMAs	District Metric Areas
EIA	Environment Impact Assessment
EIS	Environment Impact Statement
J-	Junction
P-	Pipe

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1. Chapter one: Introduction

1.0 General basis

Water scarcity is a serious issue affecting many countries around the world, and Somalia is no exception. With a combination of drought, conflict, and poor infrastructure, Somalia faces one of the most severe water crises in the world in rural specially in dry seasons. The lack of access to clean drinking water has resulted in widespread waterborne diseases, malnutrition, and even death.

Qardho, a town in the northeastern part of Somalia, after every rainy season of the year due to incompetence of water management system the town faces a severe water crisis. The lack of rainfall and a prolonged drought which have led to a shortage of water in the town, affecting the lives of its inhabitants.

In our thesis we have made a decision to plan and build a project of water supply system in one of the most populous villages in the town, Xorgoble, to provide clean and safe water to the its residents, and we believe that building this supply system is crucial in addressing this crisis of the town and in general whole country.

In our new proposed project, we will focus on the water supply system design which is aimed to serve a design population of 12,000 people, which is expected to reach more than 70,000 people Thus, the design period is fixed to be 30 years.

We are committed to make this project successful, by the wish of GOD. We eagerly look forward collaborating with all the concerned parties to accomplish our objective after we finish the design proposal of this supply project with a collective effort, we can ensure access to clean and safe water for all.

1.1 Background

1.1.1 Location of the study

Qardho is a city in the northeastern Bari region of Somalia, located 250KM through the capital of Bari region Bossaso, and 205KM from the capital of Nugaal region Garoowe, it has 4 big catchments each catchment passes $2\text{m}^3/\text{S}$ also has good groundwater, its latitude is 9.507° or $9^\circ 30' 25''$ north longitude 49.0872° or $49^\circ 5' 14''$ and Elevation of 733m above the sea level [1].

Figure 1. Geographical view of Xergoble, Qardho, Bari Region ©2023 Google Earth

1.1.2 Climate of Qardho

Qardho has a semi-desert climate. The daytime temperature is warm to hot, while it is also cold at night. You won't have rain here anytime soon. The average annual temperature for Qardho is 59° degrees and there is about 58 inches of rain in a year. It is dry for 284 days a year with an average humidity of 51% and a UV index of 7 [2].

The rainfall is concentrated in 2 rainy seasons; April-June and October-December, rain fall occurs mainly during torrential storms, the period between July-September is considered as hot season, during which strong winds prevail [3]

1.2 Objectives

1.2.1 General objective

- To design a good water supply system for Qardho, Xorgoble that enables to meet the water demand of the village by using spring water and borehole as a source

1.2.2 Specific objectives

- Access the water demand of Qardho, Xorgoble village
- Identification of potential water source
- Design and selection of pump
- Design a conveyance system for the water supply scheme of the village
- Design the reservoir capacity of the system

1.3 Methodology

The suitable methodology for this project could be a combination of surveys, data collection and analysis, and engineering design. Firstly, data can be collected on the water demand of the Xorgoble village in Qardho, as well as the potential sources of water in the area.

This can be done through surveys and interviews with the residents and local authorities. Additionally, hydrogeological surveys and tests can be conducted to identify and quantify the available groundwater resources.

Once this information is gathered, engineering design can be used to select the appropriate pumps, conveyance systems, and reservoir capacities to meet the water demand of the village.

Computer-aided design softwares will be used to model different scenarios and optimize the system such a WaterGEMS, and ArcGIS, and also presenting charts, and figures we will use Microsoft applications (Word and Excel).

Finally, the project can be implemented and monitored to ensure that it is functioning as intended and meeting the water supply needs of the village. Regular maintenance and monitoring can also be put in place to ensure the sustainability of the system over time.

2. Chapter Two: Demand assessment

2.0 Project design period

Basically, design period is defined as expected life span of a project which is almost considered to be between 20 to 50 years [4], also it gives consideration to cost of project, and level of service that the system can provide to get reliable and safe water to customers.

Therefore, the design should take into account the expected population growth, changes in water demand patterns, and potential changes in water quality and availability. It is also important to consider the maintenance and replacement needs of the system during the design period to ensure its long-term sustainability.

As we aware project design period is critical factor in ensuring that it meets the current and future needs of the community it serves. The design period in this thesis for Xorgoble water supply project is planned to be fixed in 30 years extending from 2023 to 2053.

2.0 Base population

The base population refers to the estimated population at the start of a specific period, the beginning of a design period for a water supply project. It is the starting point for estimating the future population growth in the project area, which is important in determining the water demand and the required capacity of the system.

The projections take into account factors such as birth and mortality rates, migration patterns, and economic development. It's important to note that the base population is an estimate and may be subject to change particularly in our country Somalia is based on various factors such as changes in migration patterns clan conflict, and dry season obstacles.

Therefore, it is essential to design the water supply system with the flexibility to accommodate changes in population and water demand patterns over the design period to ensure its long-term sustainability. For the projection of the population until the years 2023 and 2053, this hypothesis was verified using different mathematical formulas using the population in the year 2020 as a base year.

2.1 Population Projection

Population projections are significant in the design of water supply projects as they help to determine the expected water demand and the required capacity of the system. The projections can also help to identify potential future challenges to the water supply system, such as changes in the population growth rate or shifts in the water demand pattern.

It's imperative to state that population projections are estimates, and actual population growth may differ from the projected values. Therefore, it's essential to design the water supply system with flexibility changes in population and water demand patterns over the design period to ensure its long-term sustainability.

2.1.1 Factors affecting population growth

Population growth is influenced by a wide range of factors, both natural and social. Here are some of the important factors that affect population growth:

- Birth rate
- Death rate
- Migration
- Economic and development
- Education
- Healthcare
- War and conflict

2.1.2 Methods of population estimate

2.1.2.1 Arithmetic increase method

The arithmetic increase method is a basic technique for forecasting population growth, which assumes that the population will increase by a fixed amount every year. This method gives a low value and is suitable for well-settled and established communities.

2.1.2.2 Geometric increase method

The geometric increase method is another technique for forecasting population growth, it predicts that the population will increase by a fixed percentage every year. This method gives much higher value and is mostly applicable for growing towns and cities having vast scope for expansion.

2.1.2.3 Exponential growth rate model

The exponential growth rate model is a mathematical formula used to describe the growth of a population or a system over time. It assumes that the growth rate of the population or system is proportional to its size, which means that the larger the population or system, the faster it will grow.

2.1.2.4 Incremental increase method

The Incremental Increase Method is a simple method used to forecast population growth. It involves calculating the average annual increase in population over a certain period and then projecting this same rate of increase into the future. This method assumes a constant rate of population growth over time, but it may not always be the case due to other factors such as migration, economic trends, and government policies.

2.1.2.5 Ratio method

The Ratio Method, also called the Cohort Component Method, is a method used to forecast population growth. It involves breaking down the total population into different age groups, projecting the size and growth rates of each cohort over time, and then summing up the size of all the cohorts to get a forecast of the total population. This method is often considered more accurate than the Incremental Increase Method because it takes into account changes in the age structure of the population over time, but it may be more complex to use because it requires more data and calculations.

2.1.2.6 Geometric decrease method

The Geometric Decrease Method, also known as the Exponential Decrease Method, is a method used to forecast population decline. It involves calculating a constant rate of decline over time and using it to estimate the population size in future years. The method assumes that the population decline occurs at a decreasing rate, meaning that the population decreases by a certain percentage each year. This method is only appropriate for use in situations where the population is in decline and where the rate of decline is relatively stable over time.

2.1.2.7 Selected method

From all population forecasting methods, the geometric increase method has been found suitable for Xorgoble village. Because this method is most appropriate for use in situations where the population growth rate is between continues decline and growth.

The population in 1993 is given as equal to 2000[3]. From the given population we use the geometric increase method to calculate the population up to 2053

Step 1: Find the increase in population each decade

Year	Population
1993	2000
2003	4000
2013	7000
2023	12000

Step 2: Find the growth rate

Year	Population	Increase	Growth rate
1993	2000		
2003	4000	2000	$(2000/2000)*100=100\%$
2013	7000	3000	$(3000/4000)*100=75\%$
2023	12000	5000	$(5000/7000)*100=71\%$

Step 3: Find the average growth rate (r) using the geometrical mean.

$$R = 100 + 75 + 71 / 3 = 82$$

Step 4: Find the number of decades (n) between the last known year and the required year

$n = 3$ (3 decades elapsed between 1993 and 2023)

Step 5: Apply the formula $P_n = P_o[1 + (r/100)]^n$

$P[2053] = P[2023][1 + (82/100)]^3$

$P[2053] = 12000[1.82]^3 = 72,343$

2.2 Water demand projection

Water demand projections are important for water resource management, as they help water managers to plan for future water supply needs and ensure that sufficient water resources are available to meet the growing demand. These projections can also be useful for developing policies and programs aimed at reducing water consumption and promoting water conservation.

The projection process involves collecting and analyzing data on current water use patterns and estimating how these patterns will change over time based on a range of scenarios. The projections can then be used to guide investment in water infrastructure, such as the construction of new water treatment plants or reservoirs, and to develop conservation strategies aimed at reducing water use.

2.2.1 Factors Affecting Demand for Water

There are several factors that can affect the demand for water, including:

- Population growth
- Climate and weather
- Economic development
- Lifestyle change
- Water pricing and availability
- Technology advancement

2.2.2 Classification in Category of Demands

demands can be classified into different categories depending on their intended use. Some common categories of demands include

- Domestic
- Industrial

- Commercial
- Public use
- Livestock
- Firefighting
- Leakage

2.2.3 Domestic Water Demand

Domestic water demand refers to the amount of water used by households for activities such as drinking, cooking, cleaning, bathing, and watering plants [4]. The exact amount of domestic water demand varies depending on factors such as the number of people living in a household, their daily activities, and the climate of the region they live in. As considered the domestic consumption of village xorgoble was taken this 120 liters capita per day [4].

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Domestic water demand} &= \text{population} * \text{per capita consumption} \\ &= 72343 * 120 \\ &= 8681160 \text{ l/d} = 8681.16 \text{M}^3 \end{aligned}$$

2.2.4 Industrial Water Demand

Representing the need of industries, either existing or likely to start in the future. Its quantity will thus vary with the number and types of industries present in the city. For small-scale industries, in general, it is 50lcpd of domestic water [4].

$$= 50 * 8 = 400 \text{ l/d} = 0.4 \text{M}^3/\text{d}$$

2.2.5 Institutional and Commercial Water Demand

This is the use of institutions, such as hospitals, hotels, restaurants, schools and colleges, offices, etc. This quantity will certainly vary with the nature of the city and with the number and types of commercial establishments and institutions present in it. In small populations institutional demand is 80lcpd of domestic consumption [4].

$$80 \text{ lcpd} * 60 = 4800 \text{ l/d} = 4.8 \text{M}^3/\text{d}$$

2.2.6 Demand for Public Uses

This includes Watering in a public park, gardening, washing, sprinkling on roads, and use in a public fountain. Demand for public use is 10lpcd [4].

$$10\text{lpcd} \times 5 = 50\text{l/d} = 0.05\text{M}^3/\text{d}$$

2.2.7 Livestock water demand

Livestock water demand refers to the amount of water required by animals for various purposes such as drinking, feed production, and cleaning. It is 10% of domestic [4].

$$0.1 \times 8681.16\text{M}^3/\text{d} = 868.12\text{M}^3/\text{d}$$

2.2.8 Fire Demand

It is the amount of water required for firefighting purpose in case of a fire break out in the area. Fire demand depends on the population of the village of Xorgoble if the population is less than 70,000 demand is not calculated but it's assumed as 10% of domestic consumption [4]

$$0.1 \times 8681.16\text{M}^3/\text{d} = 868.12\text{M}^3/\text{d}$$

2.2.9 Leakage

Leakage is the amount of water loss in the water supply system to protect against leakage 0.05% of domestic is added water consumption [4].

$$0.05 \times 8681.16\text{M}^3/\text{d} = 434.58\text{M}^3/\text{d}$$

2.2.10 Average daily demand (ADD)

The average daily demand is taken to the combined total of the domestic, non-domestic, and the leakage [4].

A.D.D = demand for domestic + industrial + livestock+ public uses + commercials +leakage+ fire demand

$$= 8681.16\text{M}^3/\text{d} + 0.4\text{M}^3/\text{d} + 4.8\text{M}^3/\text{d} + 0.05\text{M}^3/\text{d} + 868.12\text{M}^3/\text{d} + 868.12\text{M}^3/\text{d} + 434.1\text{M}^3/\text{d}$$

$$= 10856.75\text{M}^3/\text{d}$$

2.2.11 Maximum daily demand (MDD)

MDD is defined as the highest day of demand in the whole year. It represents changes in demand with seasons as the local population makes use of other water sources, and is calculated as following [4].

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MDD} &= 180\% * \text{Adjusted average daily demand} \\ &= 0.18 * 10856.75 \text{M}^3/\text{d} = 1954.2 \text{M}^3/\text{d} \end{aligned}$$

2.2.12 Peak hour demand

PHD Is defined as the highest hour of the whole day. It represents the diurnal variations in the water demand resulting from the behavioral patterns of the local population [4].

2.2.13 Peak hourly Factor

The peak hour demand is the highest demand of any one hour over the maximum day [4].

Table 1 Peak Hour Factors [4]

Population	Peak factor	
< 20,000	2.0	1.8*average daily demand
20,001 – 50,000	1.9	= 1.8*1954.2M ³ /d
50,001_100,000	1.8	= 19542.1M ³ /d

3. Chapter Three: Source of Water

3.0 Introduction

One of the initial steps in the design water supply system is to determine the ultimate source of water with the demand. This involves forecasting the future water demand of the community and facility over a specified period. Once the ultimate source of water has been established, the next step is to identify potential alternative sources of water. These sources could include surface water, groundwater, or even recycled water. The goal is to identify the main and alternative sources that can meet the water demand at the most reasonable cost.

3.1 Criteria of selecting potential water sources

The choice of potential water sources for a town or city or district like Xorgoble is generally dependent on several critical factors. The first factor to consider is the location of the water source. Ideally, the source of water should be as close as possible to the district to minimize transportation costs and improve efficiency. The second factor to consider is the quantity of water available from the water source. The source of water should have sufficient water to meet the demand of the population in that area.

The quality of the water is another crucial factor to consider when selecting a water supply. The water source should be of good quality, and it should be easy and inexpensive to treat. The quality of the water is critical as it is essential for the health and wellbeing of the community. The last factor to consider when choosing a water supply is the cost of the units of the water supply schemes. The cost of the water supply system should be minimized, and it should be economically feasible for the area.

Shortly, the choice of water supply for a town or city depends on the location, quantity, quality, and cost of the water source. The selection of the water supply source is done by considering the above factors and choosing the source that provides good quality and quantity of water at the least cost. The chosen water supply must be sustainable, reliable, and cost-effective in the long term to ensure the community's water needs are met for designed years to come.

3.2 Hydro geology of the area

Generally, the hydrogeology of North eastern region of Somalia (Puntland) is defined by four distinct geological features and drainage basins, namely, the coastal belt and sloping plain in the Gulf of Arden Basin; valleys that include the Nugaal and Darroor; the Mudug Galgaduud Plateau in the Ogaaden Basin; and the coastal belt in the coastal basin [1].

Qardho which is the town that Xorgoble is located is situated on limestone and gypsy-ferrous formations, these formations have a nature to dissolve and create what is known as (Karstic depressions) or sink holes. Water bearing layers are found within these layers as water is hard more than 2500 micro/homs with high content of calcium carbonates, and magnesium sulphates [2].

3.2.1 Hydro geological units and aquifer systems

Water aquifers in this area are often found in alluvial deposits within the old river bed channels, the Karkaar, and Taleex formations, and mainly majority of wells drilled within these materials from later geologic times produce hard water often with a high content of sulphates, bicarbonates, carbonates, chlorides, etc.

out of the nine hydrogeological units which belong to the major six aquifer systems classified in the study area, four are most promising for further development and groundwater utilization. They are: Major Togga alluviums (inter-granular aquifer of Quaternary age), Jurassic lime-stones (karstic aquifer), lime-stones (karstic aquifer of Lower Eocene age), and Karkaar lime-stones (karstic aquifer of Upper Eocene). The best transmissivity values were obtained from pumping tests of the wells drilled in alluviums and lime-stones.

The estimated actual recharge and permeability of four major aquifers was roughly concluded an equivalent average flow from these major aquifer systems (dynamic reserves) could be equal to 139 m³ /s [5].

3.2.2 Water quality and aquifer chemistry in the area

Groundwater quality and chemical composition is a result of soil and geological formations through which the water has residence time, effective recharge, groundwater depth as well as pollutants if they are presented in the catchment area.

Physical properties and concentrations of chemical components in groundwater vary widely within areas, depending on the location and type of water sources (spring, dug well, drilled well) [6].

Table 2 Values of Analyzed Groundwater quality parameters in North eastern region of Somalia (Puntland) [6]

	<i>Number of samples</i>	<i>pH</i>		<i>EC (μS/cm)</i>		<i>T °C</i>	
Drilled well	147	6	10	160	11000	21	38
Dug well	370	7	10	271	11000	19	36
Spring	61	6	8	596	7840	22	37

The obtained data of chemical parameters from the laboratories are analyzed in terms of the spatial position and related quality, and on the other hand in terms of the relationship between the aquifer and the groundwater quality.

More than 511 samples are tested to obtain minimal, maximal and average values or concentrations of major characteristics in different potential elements as discussed *Table 3*

Table 3 Min. Max. and Average Values of Analyzed Groundwater Chemical Parameters [6]

Parameter	<i>Minimum</i>	<i>Maximum</i>	<i>Average</i>
EC (μS/cm)	271	9 480	3 539.07
PH	6	10	7.68
TEMP (°C)	19	38	26.40
Chloride (mg/l)	7.6	4 330	600.83
Sulfate (mg/l)	24	8 930	1 653.39
Nitrate (mg/l)	0.9	168	31.38
Nitrite (mg/l)	0.02	0.48	0.12
Ammonium (mg/l)	0.07	58	15.01
Fluoride (mg/l)	0.2	8.4	1.82
Hydrogen Carbonate (mg/l)	112	567	272.41
Carbonate (mg/l)	5	10	7.86

Aluminum (mg/l)	0.09	0.19	0.13
Arsenic (mg/l)	0.005	0.026	0.01
Barium (mg/l)	0.005	0.2	0.05
Lead (mg/l)	0.005	0.009	0.01
Boron (mg/l)	0.07	4.5	0.92
Cadmium (mg/l)	0.001	0.002	0.00
Calcium (mg/l)	21.6	825	305.03
Chromium (mg/l)	0.005	0.025	0.01
Iron (mg/l)	0.02	0.12	0.07
Potassium (mg/l)	1.7	111	21.54
Copper (mg/l)	0.005	0.012	0.01
Magnesium (mg/l)	8.41	2330	180.18
Manganese (mg/l)	0.006	4.2	0.89
Sodium (mg/l)	9.6	2530	353.28
Phosphorus total (mg/l)	0.05	0.11	0.07
Mercury (mg/l)	0	0	0.00
Silica (mg/l)	4.9	40	14.22
Strontium (mg/l)	0.51	21	7.05
Zinc (mg/l)	0.01	1.9	0.43
Iodine (mg/l)	0.006	2.6	0.27

3.3 Proposed water supply resource

3.3.1 Borehole source

To satisfy the future demand we concluded to use borehole source rather than other sources, as the others cannot give sufficient demand in the village, at the moment there is one borehole in the village it is 250m deep and has 8.7l/s as per the pump-rated on recorded data.[7]

Maximum discharges of the proposed boreholes were understood from existing wells around the town at average yield of 21l/s [7]

So, we have to know how many boreholes are enough to satisfy our peak hourly demand using this formula below here

$$= \frac{\text{max. daydemand} \times 2053 \times \text{safetyfactor}}{\text{safeyield}}$$

$$\frac{226.2L/s \times 1.2}{21L/s} = 13 \text{ bore holes}$$

Existing borehole = 1

Total required boreholes = 13-1= 12 boreholes

4. Chapter Four: Design of Pressure Line

4.0 Pipe diameter

Pipe diameter is first factor that determines whether your system moves an adequate volume of fluid. Here we Optimized pipe size and velocity that can increase the service life of our system. By caring move at an increased velocity, higher velocity can accelerate the damage rate, increasing corrosion and pitting.

4.1 Economical pumping Mains Diameter

To determine the economical pumping mains diameter for water, we'll need to consider a few factors. The main factors that will impact the diameter of the pipe required are the flow rate, the distance the water needs to be pumped, the properties of the water being pumped, and the cost of energy [7].

$$Q = A * V$$

Where, Q = discharge (m³/s)

V = permissible velocity (0.6 to 1.50m/s)

A = Cross-sectional area of pipe (m²)

The size of the pipe used in the water distribution system can be determined by following formulas [7]:

1. Darcy –Welsbach formula; $h_f = \frac{fLV^2}{2gD}$
2. Hazen-William's formula; $Q = 0.278CD^{2.63}S^{0.54}$, $S = \frac{h_f}{L}$
3. Manning's Formula; $Q = \frac{1AR^{2/3}S^{1/2}}{n}$
4. Lee formula; $D = 0.97 \text{ to } 1.22\sqrt{Q}$

Lee's formula is commonly and the most efficient used in determining the diameter of the pumping mains.

$$D = 0.97 \text{ to } 1.22 \sqrt{Q}$$

Where D = Economical diameter of pipe in meters

Q = Required discharge of water to be pumped in m³/sec.

For safety we took the larger coefficient i.e. 1.22 The discharge to be 120% of the safe yield.

Q=21L/s =0.021m³/s (discharge from well)

$$D=1.22\sqrt{1.2 * Q}$$

$$D=1.22\sqrt{1.2 * 0.021} =195\text{mm}$$

Check for velocity:

$$V = \frac{Q}{A} \quad \text{Where } Q = \text{required discharge of water to be pumped in m}^3/\text{s}$$

A = area of pumping in m²

$$A = \frac{\pi}{4} D^2 = \frac{\pi}{4} (0.195)^2 = 0.0094 \text{ m}^2$$

$$V = \frac{0.021}{0.0094} = 2.23 \text{ m/s}$$

Therefore, the velocity is correct since it is within the allowable limit of 0.6 to 1.5m/s.

4.2 Selection of pipe material

When selecting a pipe material, there are several factors that need to be considered based on the specific application. Some of the key factors are:

- **Pressure and Temperature:** The maximum pressure and temperature that the pipe will be exposed to during operation should also be taken into account when choosing the pipe material.
- **Installation Environment:** The installation environment, including soil conditions and potential exposure to sunlight, can impact the durability and longevity of the pipe material.
- **Cost:** The cost of the pipe material is another important consideration, as it can affect the overall cost of the project.
- **Maintenance:** The maintenance requirements of the pipe material should also be considered in terms of cost and ease of access. For the Xorgoble water supply project, PVC pipes are selected for the distribution system, PVC pipes are lightweight, easy to install, and resistant to corrosion and chemicals.

4.3 Design of pipe lines

The design of a pipeline typically involves several steps, including determining the required flow rate, selecting an appropriate pipe material, sizing the pipe, and designing the system layout as discussed here:

- **Determine the Required Flow Rate:** The first step is to determine the required flow rate based on the specific application. This involves calculating the amount of fluid that needs to be transported through the pipe per unit of time.
- **Select an Appropriate Pipe Material:** As I mentioned earlier, selecting a pipe material involves considering factors such as fluid properties, pressure and temperature, installation environment, cost, and maintenance.
- **Size of the Pipe:** The pipe size is determined based on the required flow rate, pipe material, and pressure drop calculations. The pressure drop calculation involves considering the length of the pipe, the diameter of the pipe, and the frictional losses due to fluid flow.

- Design the System Layout: The final step is to design the system layout, which involves determining the number of pipes required, the pipe routing, the location of valves and fittings, and any additional equipment required, such as pumps or pressure regulators.

As there are no direct method instructed to use in this design, we'll follow these steps, one after one, first of all the diameters of the pipes are assumed, the terminal pressure heads which could be made available at the end of each pipe line after allowing for the loss of pressure head in the pipe link when full peak flow discharge is flowing are then determined. The determination of the friction losses in each pipe line is done. The total discharge flowing through the main pipes is to be determined in advance.

5. Chapter Five: Pumps

5.0 Pump basis

A pump is a mechanical device that is used to move fluids, such as liquids or gases, from one place to another. It works by creating a low-pressure region at the inlet of the pump, which causes the fluid to be drawn in.

The pump then increases the pressure of the fluid and discharges it through the outlet. Pumps are commonly used in a wide range of applications, including water supply, heating and cooling systems, chemical processing, oil and gas production, and many more.

There are several different types of pumps, including centrifugal pumps, positive displacement pumps, and axial flow pumps, each of which are designed for specific applications and have their unique characteristics.

5.1 Purpose of Pump

In water systems, pumps are commonly used to transport water from one location to another, either to increase the water pressure or to move water across distances. The primary purpose of pumps in water systems is to ensure that water is delivered to where it is needed with sufficient pressure, flow rate, and reliability.

Some specific purposes of pumps in water systems are:

- Water supply: Pumps are used to pump water from underground wells or surface water sources such as lakes or rivers, to supply water to households, industries, and irrigation systems.
- Water treatment: Pumps are used to transport water to and from treatment plants, where it is treated to remove impurities or contaminants.
- Water distribution: Pumps are used to distribute the treated water to different locations within a distribution network, such as homes, buildings, and reservoirs.
- Fire protection: Pumps are used in fire protection systems, where they are used to increase the water pressure and flow rate to ensure that there is sufficient water to extinguish fires.

- Wastewater treatment: Pumps are used in wastewater treatment systems to transport wastewater to and from different treatment stages.

Overall, pumps play a critical role in ensuring that water is supplied, treated, and transported reliably and efficiently to meet the needs of communities and industries.

5.2 Selection of A pump

When selecting a pump for water supply distribution, several factors need to be considered, including the required flow rate, pressure, power consumption, and the specific application. Here are some of the key factors to consider:

- Flow Rate: The flow rate is the volume of water that needs to be delivered per unit of time. It is important to select a pump that can handle the required flow rate for the specific application.
- Pressure: Pressure is the force of the water that needs to be delivered, and it is important to select a pump that can deliver the required pressure for the specific application.
- Power Consumption: The power consumption of the pump is an important consideration, as it affects the running cost of the pump over its lifetime. It is important to select a pump that is efficient and has a low running cost.
- Type of Pump: Several types of pumps can be used for water supply distribution, including centrifugal pumps, positive displacement pumps, and turbine pumps. Each type of pump has its unique characteristics, and it is important to select the appropriate type for the specific application.
- Maintenance Requirements: The maintenance requirements of the pump should also be considered, as regular maintenance is necessary to ensure that the pump operates reliably and efficiently over its lifetime.
- Cost: The cost of the pump is also an important consideration, as it affects the overall cost of the project.

It is important to consult with a qualified engineer or a pumping expert to ensure that the pump selected is suitable for the specific application and meets all necessary standards and regulations.

5.3 Centrifugal Pump

Centrifugal pumps are a type of pump that we will use in this water supply distribution systems, because they are preferred for the supply and distribution systems as they are simple in design, easy to install and maintain, and can handle a wide range of flow rates and pressures. They are also highly efficient, as the kinetic energy generated by the impeller is converted into potential energy with minimal energy losses due to friction.

The basic components of a centrifugal pump include an impeller, a volute casing, and an inlet and outlet. The impeller consists of a series of blades that rotate at high speed when the pump is in operation, creating a low-pressure region at the center of the impeller.

The fluid is then drawn into the impeller from the inlet and propelled outwards by the centrifugal force generated by the rotating blades. The fluid is then channeled into the volute casing, which gradually increases the cross-sectional area of the flow path, converting the kinetic energy of the fluid into potential energy, which increases the pressure of the fluid as it exits the pump through the outlet.

However, centrifugal pumps are not suitable for applications that require high pressure and low flow rates or for handling viscous fluids. In these cases, positive displacement pumps may be a better choice.

5.4 Position of a pumping station and service Reservoir

In water supply distribution systems, the position of the pumping station and service reservoir is important to ensure that the water is delivered reliably and efficiently to consumers. Here are some factors to consider when determining the location of a pumping station and service reservoir:

Geographical Location: The location should be easily accessible and located in a strategic position that allows for efficient water distribution.

Topography: The topography of the area should be taken into account, as the position of the pumping station and service reservoir will impact the head (the difference in elevation between the two points), which affects the pressure and flow rate of the water.

Water Demand: The water demand of the area should be considered, as this will determine the pumping capacity required and the size of the service reservoir.

Water Source: The distance from the water source should be taken into account, as this will impact the cost of pumping the water to the service reservoir.

Cost: The cost of constructing and maintaining the pumping station and service reservoir should also be considered, as this will impact the overall cost of the project.

The service reservoir should be located at a higher elevation than the distribution network to ensure that there is sufficient head to deliver the water to consumers with the required pressure, the position of the service reservoir about the distribution network is proposed at an elevation of 738m above mean sea level at a distance of 752m from the reserve area and the service reservoir is located at 795m above mean sea.

5.5 Design of the well

In this water supply system, the well is typically used as a holding tank to store water before it is pumped to a higher elevation. The Xorgoble well is situated 1.5 km far from the village center in the north direction.

5.6 Design criteria

Assumed pumping hours = 22hours

The required time to be stored = 2hours

The maximum discharge of the well ($Q_{max.}$) = 21l/s

Volume (V) = time* Q_{max}

$$V = 2*60*60sec*0.021m^3/s$$

$$V = 151.2m^3$$

$$V = 152m^3$$

The well has a capacity of about 152m³ and will be constructed from a reinforced concrete structure and will have an internal area of 100m² with a depth of 1.8m. From the well to the service reservoir water is lifted by pumping.

5.7 Diameter of the delivery pipe

$$Q = 211/s = 0.021m^3/s$$

Assume flow velocity of 1.0m/s which is recommended between 0.6 to 1.5 m/s [].

$$D = \sqrt{\frac{4*Q}{\pi*V}}$$

$$D = \sqrt{\frac{4*0.021}{\pi*1.0}}$$

$$D = 0.164m = 164mm \text{ (diameter of resevior - well)}$$

Take pipe size=160mm

Check for velocity

$$V = \frac{4*Q}{\pi D^2}$$

$$V = \frac{4*0.021}{\pi*0.16^2}$$

$$V = 1.05m/s$$

V = 1.05m/s (velocity of water flow between the well and the reservoir)

5.8 Raw water pump capacity determination

The total head against which the pump should work includes discharge lift and total head losses.

$$\text{Friction loss Head loss (hf)} = [10.67*Q^{1.852}/C^{1.852}*D^{4.8704}] *L$$

C= Roughness Coefficient 150

$$D = 0.16m$$

$$Q = 0.021 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$$

$$L = 752 \text{ m}$$

$$HF = [10.67 * 0.021^{1.852} / 150^{1.852} * 0.16^{4.8704}] * 752$$

$$HF = 4.4 \text{ m}$$

5.9 Minor losses

Entrance loss (H_i) = $0.04V^2/2g$ for bell-mouthed entrance.

Where, V is the flow velocity through the conduit

$$H_i = 0.04 * 1.05^2 / 2 * 9.81 = 0.00224$$

Gate and valve loss (H_g) = $0.2V$ taken for the fully open gate and butterfly valve

$$H_g = 0.2 * 1.05^2 / 2 * 9.81 = 0.0112$$

Exit loss (H_e) = $V^2/2g$

$$H_e = 1.05^2 / 2 * 9.81 = 0.0562 \text{ m}$$

Total minor loss = Entrance loss + Gate and valve loss + Exit loss

$$= 0.00224 + 0.0112 + 0.0562 = 0.0707$$

Total head loss = friction loss + minor loss

$$= 0.0707 + 4.4 \text{ m} = 4.4707 = 4.48 \text{ m}$$

Therefore, total head required by pump = reservoir elevation – elevation of well + total head loss

$$H_T = 798 \text{ m} - 735 \text{ m} + 4.48 \text{ m} = 67.48 \text{ m}$$

The power required to drive the pump is given by [4]

$$P = \frac{\gamma_w Q H_T}{\eta}$$

Where:

γ_w = Specific density of water (1000)

η = Efficiency of a pump (70%)

Q = Discharge in m³/s

H = Total head in meters

P = Power of pump in KW

$$P = \frac{1000 * 0.021 * 67.48}{0.7}$$

$$P = 2.02 \text{KW}$$

5.10 Power of generator

A power generator is a device that converts mechanical energy into electrical energy. It works by using a fuel source, such as gasoline or diesel, to power a motor that turns an alternator to produce electricity. The electrical power generated by the generator can be used for a variety of purposes, such as providing electricity to a home or business during power outages or remote locations where there is no access to a reliable power grid. Power generators come in various sizes and capacities to accommodate different power requirements, and they can be portable or stationary depending on the intended use.

In general power of the generator (P_g) is 150% times the power of the pump [4].

$$P_g = 1.5 * P$$

Take For safety purposes recommend the power of the generator 1.1* times the power of the pump by taking 40% for allowance.

$$P_g = 1.1 * P = 1.1 * 2.02 = 2.23 \text{KW}$$

6. Chapter Six: Service Reservoir

6.0 Service reservoir basis

A service reservoir is a type of reservoir that is used in water supply systems to store treated water, which is then distributed to homes and businesses. Service reservoirs are typically located at high points in the distribution system, such as on hilltops or elevated ground, to provide sufficient pressure for the water to flow to lower elevations. The stored water in service reservoirs helps to maintain a consistent and reliable supply of water, especially during periods of high demand or when there are disruptions in the supply system. Service reservoirs can be made of concrete, steel, or other materials and can range in size from small tanks to large structures holding millions of gallons of water.

6.1 Service Reservoir Necessity

Service reservoirs are necessary for water supply systems for several reasons.

- Firstly, they provide a buffer between water treatment plants and the distribution system, allowing for a consistent supply of water to be maintained even when there are fluctuations in demand or disruptions in the treatment plant or distribution system.
- Secondly, service reservoirs help to maintain water pressure in the distribution system, especially in areas of high elevation. By storing water at higher elevations, the service reservoirs provide the necessary pressure to ensure that water can flow to lower elevations and homes and businesses throughout the distribution system.
- Finally, service reservoirs provide a reserve of water in case of emergencies, such as power outages, pipeline breaks, or other disruptions to the supply system. This reserve of water can help to ensure that there is always enough water available for drinking, cooking, and other needs, even during unexpected events

6.2 Design capacity and location

The design capacity and location of service reservoirs depend on several factors, such as the size of the community or service area, water demand, topography, and available space.

The design capacity of a service reservoir is typically based on the maximum daily demand for water, plus a reserve capacity to account for emergencies, system maintenance, and other factors. The location of the reservoir is often determined by the topography of the area, with reservoirs typically located at high points in the distribution system, such as on hills or elevated ground, to provide the necessary pressure for water to flow to lower elevations.

6.3 Reservoir type

Service reservoirs can be constructed using a variety of materials, depending on the specific needs and requirements of the water supply system. The operational processes within the water and other industries dealing with fluids often require circular structures to ensure their systems of work are carried out efficiently and economically. Hence circular tank is chosen for the design of the Xorgoble village water supply.

6.4 Accessories of Service Reservoirs

Service reservoirs may have several accessories or features that are designed to enhance their functionality, safety, and reliability. Some of these accessories include:

- Inlet and Outlet Pipes: These are pipes that allow water to enter and exit the reservoir. They are usually located at the bottom of the reservoir to ensure that the water is fresh and clean.
- Overflow Pipes: These are pipes that are designed to prevent the reservoir from overflowing during heavy rainfall or other events. They allow excess water to flow out of the reservoir and into nearby rivers or streams.
- Valves: Valves are used to control the flow of water into and out of the reservoir. They are typically located at the inlet and outlet pipes and can be manually or automatically operated.

- Ladders and Stairways: These are used to provide access to the reservoir for maintenance and inspection purposes. They are usually made of steel and are designed to be safe and secure.
- Level Indicators: These are devices that are used to monitor the water level in the reservoir. They can be automatic or manual and are essential for ensuring that the reservoir is functioning properly.
- Fencing and Security Features: Service reservoirs may be surrounded by fencing or other security features to prevent unauthorized access and ensure public safety.

6.5 Depth and shape

6.5.1 The depth

Depth of a service reservoir can vary depending on several factors, including the capacity of the reservoir, the size of the distribution system, and the topography of the area. In general, service reservoirs are designed to be deep enough to maintain a consistent and reliable water supply to the distribution system.

The depth of a service reservoir can also affect the water pressure in the distribution system. If the reservoir is too shallow, it may not provide enough pressure to distribute water to areas at higher elevations. On the other hand, if the reservoir is too deep, it may require additional pumping systems to move the water to the distribution system.

The depth of a service reservoir is typically determined by the design engineers who are responsible for the water supply system. They will take into account factors such as the size of the community or service area, water demand, topography, and available space to determine the appropriate depth for the reservoir. Ultimately, the depth of a service reservoir will depend on the specific needs and characteristics of the water supply system it serves.

The depths most usually used are as follows.

Size (m ³)	Depth of water (m)
Up to 3500	2.5 – 3.5
3500 – 15,000	3.5 – 5 .0
Over 15,000	5.0 – 7.0

6.5.2 Shape

A circular reservoir is geometrically the most economical shape giving the least amount of walling for a given volume and depth.

6.6 Reservoir Capacity Determination

The determination of service reservoir capacity is a complex process that requires careful consideration of several factors. Here are some of the factors that are typically taken into account when determining the capacity of a service reservoir:

- **Water Demand:** The capacity of a service reservoir will depend on the maximum daily demand for water in the community or service area. This demand can be affected by factors such as population growth, industry, and climate.
- **Water Storage Requirements:** The service reservoir needs to have enough storage capacity to ensure that there is enough water available during periods of high demand, such as hot summer months or droughts.
- **Peak Hour Demand:** The service reservoir must be able to meet peak hour demand, which is typically the highest level of demand during the day. This can be affected by factors such as industrial usage, peak-hour bathing, and lawn watering.
- **Emergency Supply:** The service reservoir must have enough storage capacity to meet emergency supply needs, such as firefighting, in case of a disaster or other emergency.
- **Pipeline Maintenance:** The service reservoir must have enough storage capacity to provide water to the distribution system during pipeline maintenance or other disruptions in the water supply system.

Table 4 Reservoir Capacity Determination (Analytical Method)

Maximum daily demand					
Hour	Hourly demand variation factor	Supply (m ³ /h)	Consumption (m ³ /h)	Storage (m ³ /h)	Cumulative storage(m ³)
0	0.3	453	136	317	317
1	0.3	453	136	317	634
2	0.3	453	136	317	951
3	0.3	453	136	317	1268
4	0.3	453	136	317	1585
5	0.7	453	317	136	1721
6	1.1	453	498	-45	1676
7	1.9	453	861	-408	1268
8	1.7	453	770	-317	951
9	1.5	453	679.5	-226.5	724.5
10	1.5	453	679.5	-226.5	498.5
11	1.4	453	634	-181	317
12	1.4	453	634	-181	136
13	1.3	453	589	-136	0
14	1.2	453	544	-91	-91

15	1.5	453	679	-226.5	-317.5
16	1.6	453	725	-272	-589.5
17	1.5	453	679	-226.5	-816
18	1.3	453	589	-136	-952
19	1	453	453	0	-952
20	0.7	453	317	136	-816
21	0.5	453	226	227	-589
22	0.4	453	181	272	-317
23	0.3	453	136	317	0

Table 5 Concluded Volume Determination Data

Years	Maximum	Maximum	Reservoir	Volume of
	Storage (m ³)	Deficit (m ³)	Capacity(m ³)	Reservoir(m ³)
2023-2053	1721	952	2673	2673

The capacity of the previous reservoir = 1000m³

Capacity of reservoir = (2673-1000) m³ = 1673m³

For safety provide a reservoir with a capacity of 1700m³

6.7 Height determination of the reservoir

Assume, $H = 5.5\text{m}$ [7]

$$V = \pi \frac{D^2 H}{4} \text{ where, } V = \text{Volume of reservoir (m}^3\text{)}$$

$D = \text{Diameter of reservoir (m)}$

$H = \text{Height of reservoir (m)}$

$$1800\text{m}^3 = \frac{\pi D^2 * 5.5}{4}$$

$$D = \sqrt[4]{417} = 20.41\text{m, } \sim 20\text{m}$$

6.8 Methods of Distribution

There are several methods of water distribution from service reservoirs to communities or businesses. Here are some of the most common methods:

- Gravity Flow: This is the simplest and most common method of water distribution. Water flows from the service reservoir to the distribution system by gravity, which provides the necessary pressure to maintain a consistent flow of water.
- Pumping: In cases where the distribution system is at a higher elevation than the service reservoir, pumping is necessary to move the water from the reservoir to the distribution system. Pumping can also be used to increase pressure in areas of low elevation or high demand.
- Combination of Gravity Flow and Pumping: In some cases, a combination of gravity flow and pumping is used to distribute water from the service reservoir to the distribution system. This allows for the advantages of both methods to be utilized.
- Pressure System: In a pressure system, water is distributed to the community or business at constant pressure. This method is often used in high-rise buildings or areas with uneven topography where gravity flow is not sufficient to provide the necessary pressure.

- District Metered Areas (DMAs): DMAs are used to manage water distribution in large service areas. They divide the distribution system into smaller areas that are metered and monitored separately to ensure that water is distributed efficiently and equitably.

6.8.1 Gravity Distribution

The method of gravity distribution is appropriate for the village in a simple way that we have the best topography for the reservoir so taking this method has good distribution based on geographical various factor.

Figure 2. Gravity distribution view in ArcGIS

7. Chapter Seven: Environmental Impact Assessment

7.0 General

An Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) is a process that evaluates the potential environmental impacts of a proposed project or development. The purpose of an EIA is to identify, predict and evaluate the potential environmental effects of a proposed project on the environment, as well as to identify measures to avoid, minimize or mitigate those impacts.

The EIA process typically involves several stages, beginning with scoping to identify the key issues and potential impacts, followed by baseline studies to establish the current environmental conditions and assess the potential impacts of the proposed project. The next stage involves impact assessment and evaluation, which may include modeling and monitoring to predict and quantify the magnitude and significance of the impacts. This information is then used to develop appropriate mitigation measures to avoid or reduce the negative impacts on the environment.

Public participation is often a key component of the EIA process, with opportunities for stakeholders and the public to provide input and feedback. The findings of the EIA are typically documented in an Environmental Impact Statement (EIS) or Environmental Assessment (EA), which is submitted to the relevant regulatory authority for review and decision-making

7.1 Potential Adverse Impact

When assessing a water supply system project, potential adverse impacts on the environment must be considered. Some of the potential impacts on water supply systems might include:

- Soil
- Water resource

7.2 Impact on the natural soil

The construction activities for the pressure and distribution lines and reservoirs will have some impact on soil. The activities are trenches for pipes and earthwork for the reservoirs. Though the soil is put back to its place, the natural structure and its compaction can't fully be achieved. This will in turn expose the soil for erosion. Thus, to prevent this problem or for the soil to be affected

slightly, most of the pipelines can be laid in area having already disturbed soil structures, for instance, a side roads or on farm lands(for transmission lines and reservoir)

7.3 Impact on water resources

To prevent lowering of the water table due to over-extraction of water, there are several measures that can be taken:

- Implement water conservation measures: By encouraging water conservation, the demand for water can be reduced, which in turn can help to prevent over-extraction of water from the water table.
- Develop alternative water sources: Alternative water sources such as rainwater harvesting, treated wastewater, or desalinated water can help to reduce the demand on groundwater resources.
- Implement water use restrictions: Water use restrictions such as limiting irrigation or other non-essential water uses during drought periods can help to reduce the demand on groundwater.
- Implement recharge measures: Recharge measures such as artificial recharge or reforestation can help to recharge groundwater resources and prevent over-extraction.
- Monitor and manage groundwater resources: Implementing a groundwater monitoring program and establishing sustainable management practices can help to prevent over-extraction of groundwater and maintain the water table at a sustainable level.

By incorporating these measures into the design and operation of the water supply system, the potential adverse impacts of lowering of the water table can be mitigated. These measures can be identified and evaluated through the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) process, which can help to ensure the sustainable use of groundwater resources and protect the environment

7.4 Potential positive impacts

When conducting an Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) for our water supply system project, we see that's important to not only consider the potential adverse impacts, but also the potential positive impacts. Some potential positive impacts of Xergoble water supply system project may include:

- Improved access to clean and reliable drinking water: A well-designed and properly operated water supply system can improve access to clean and reliable drinking water, which can improve public health and quality of life.
- Increased agricultural productivity: Improved water availability can enable increased agricultural productivity, which can improve food security and economic development.
- Conservation of natural ecosystems: By providing alternative water sources and reducing the demand on groundwater, a water supply system can help to conserve natural ecosystems and support aquatic habitats.
- Economic development: A water supply system can support economic development by enabling industrial and commercial activities that require a reliable water supply.
- Increased property values: Improved access to water can increase property values, which can have economic benefits for property owners and the local community.

7.5 Socio-economic impact

Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) for Xorgoble water supply system project is considering the socio-economic impacts of the project on the local communities including:

- Improved health and sanitation: The availability of clean water can improve public health and sanitation, which can result in reduced healthcare costs and improved quality of life.
- Increased economic development: A water supply system can support economic development by enabling industrial and commercial activities that require a reliable water supply, which can result in increased employment opportunities and economic growth.
- Improved education: Improved access to water can result in improved school attendance and performance, especially for girls who often bear the burden of water collection.
- Increased property values: Improved access to water can increase property values, which can result in economic benefits for property owners and the local community.
- Social empowerment: By involving local communities in the planning and development of the water supply system, the project can contribute to social empowerment and capacity building.

7.6 Health related impact

It is important to consider the health-related impacts of the project. Some potential health-related impacts of a water supply system project may include:

- Improved access to safe drinking water: A water supply system can provide access to safe drinking water, which can reduce the incidence of waterborne diseases such as cholera, typhoid, and dysentery.
- Improved sanitation: A water supply system can also improve sanitation by providing water for hygiene and sanitation purposes, which can reduce the incidence of hygiene-related diseases such as diarrhea and skin infections.
- Reduced exposure to contaminants: A well-designed and properly operated water supply system can help to reduce exposure to contaminants such as heavy metals, pesticides, and pathogens, which can have negative health impacts.
- Improved nutrition: A water supply system can support agricultural productivity, which can result in increased access to nutritious food and improved nutrition.
- Improved mental health and well-being: Improved access to water can reduce the burden of water collection, especially for women and girls, which can contribute to improved mental health and well-being.

8. Chapter Eight: Conclusion and Recommendation

8.0 Conclusion

In conclusion, the Water Supply Project in Xorgoble, Qardho, Bari Region will be significant stride in addressing the water scarcity and improving the quality of life for the residents. The project will successfully implement the construction of a reliable and sustainable water supply system, providing clean and accessible water to the community. This would be a positive impact on various aspects, including health, sanitation, education, and economic opportunities. Moreover than that, the project will have instrumental in enhancing the overall well-being of the residents, especially women and children who previously faced significant hardships in obtaining safe water.

Furthermore, we wish to get collaborative efforts between the local authorities, NGOs, and community members that may have play a vital role in the success of the project. The active participation and engagement of the community throughout the planning and implementation stages will foster a sense of ownership, ensuring the sustainability of the water supply system for years to come. The project will also create employment opportunities, empowering the local workforce and stimulating the local economy.

8.1 Recommendation

As technology advances, people's living standards improve, leading to an increase in water consumption. This rise in demand comes from commercial, domestic, public, and unaccounted losses. Therefore, there is a need for additional water sources to meet the town's requirements. Once the project is completed, it is important to organize the community to ensure the long-term sustainability of the water supply system.

Controlling practices that affect the quality of groundwater is crucial around the well and spring areas. To maintain the project throughout its design period, all components of the structure should be constructed under the supervision of qualified personnel. Addressing the extra water losses in the town and specially in Xorgoble village requires continuous awareness campaigns on proper water usage by the community administration and other responsible entities. This project design requires efficient time to complete all detail structural design analysis and cost. However, the time allowed to do it is not enough to run the work successfully, so there's need further work.

APPENDIXES

Appendix A: Water quality test results

Parameters	mg/L as CaCO ₃	Conductivity	252µs/Cm
Total hardness	56	Turbidity	0 NTU
Calcium hardness	28	Temperature	25.1 °C
Magnesium hardness	28	T.D.S	126 mg/L
Total alkalinity	75	Total Cl ₂	0.21 mg/L
Bicarbonate alkalinity	75	PH	7.0
Hydroxide alkalinity	0.0	Silica(SO ₂)	—
Carbonate alkalinity	0.0		
Dissolved NH ₃	0.09 mg/L		

Cat ions	mg/L	meq/L	Anions	mg/L	meq/L
Na ⁺¹	22.01	0.9572	Cl ⁻	1.5	0.0423
NH ₄ ⁺¹	0.09	0.0050	F ⁻	1	0.0526
K ⁺¹	8.00	0.2046	HCO ₃ ⁻¹	91.5	1.4997
Ca ²⁺	11.20	0.5589	NO ₃ ⁻¹	0.22	0.0035
Mg ²⁺	6.72	0.5530	NO ₂ ⁻¹	0.02	0.0005
Fe ²⁺	0.05	0.0018	Br ⁻¹	0.38	0.0048
Cu ²⁺	0.08	0.0025	CO ₃ ⁻²	—	—
Mn ²⁺	0.00	0.0000	SO ₄ ⁻²	2	0.0416
Cr ⁶⁺	0.00	0.0000	PO ₄ ⁻³	20.2	0.6381
Total		2.2830			2.2831

Remark:	The analyzed water sample is Physio-chemically fit for drinking
Reported: on 4/12/2018 by FAO under SWALIM	

Appendix B: Network nodes result – Junctions and Pipes

Label	Elevation	Demand	Label	Length	Diameter
J-1	734.4	21	Unit	m	mm
J-2	731.6	21	P-1	356	195
J-3	734.2	21	P-2	135	195
J-4	737.9	21	P-3	444	195
J-5	737.8	21	P-4	437	195
J-6	738.8	21	P-5	160	195
J-7	734.9	21	P-6	142	195
J-8	736.4	21	P-7	82	195
J-9	734.3	21	P-8	178	195
J-10	733.3	21	P-9	35	195
J-11	733.8	21	P-10	41	195
J-12	732.6	21	P-11	223	195
J-13	732	21	P-12	61	195
J-14	732.3	21	P-13	51	195
J-15	732.3	21	P-14	210	195
J-16	732.1	21	P-15	203	195
J-17	732.5	21	P-16	350	195
J-18	733.2	21	P-17	100	195
J-19	733.6	21	P-18	184	195
J-20	734.1	21	P-19	214	195
J-21	734.7	21	P-20	123	195
J-22	735	42	P-21	223	195
J-23	735	21	P-22	177	195
J-24	734.7	21	P-23	190	195
J-25	734.4	21	P-24	100	195
J-26	734.1	21	P-25	40	195
J-27	735.4	21	P-26	60	195
J-28	735.3	21	P-27	240	195
J-29	734.1	21	P-28	154	195
J-30	735.2	21	P-29	38	195
J-31	735.6	21	P-30	20	195
J-32	733.6	21	P-31	200	195
J-33	735.2	21	P-32	191	195
J-34	733.9	21	P-33	39	195
J-35	735	21	P-34	200	195
J-36	733.8	21	P-35	210	195
J-37	735.2	21	P-36	221	195

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